

Time-domain modeling of a fixed detached oscillating water column towards a floating multi-chamber device.

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Abstract

A simplified time-domain model for a fixed detached Oscillating Water Column (OWC) device is presented as a first step towards modeling a floating multi-chamber OWC device. The motion of a floating body in the time-domain is expressed by Cummins integro-differential equation, and based on it, water mass motion inside the chamber has been modeled here as a piston-like motion. Radiation, hydrostatic, excitation and viscous forces have been considered, as well as the added mass of the water in the chamber and the effect of the air pressure inside it. The equation of the floating body in the time domain has been approximated by a state-space method, which comes from the extension of the state-space system corresponding to the convolution integral of the radiation force. Experimental data have been used for model calibration and validation. Furthermore, the model has also been validated

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with a widely used Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model (IH-2VOF). These show that the model presented is reliable and computationally efficient allowing for massive simulations for a statistical design or economic feasibility studies.

Keywords: Oscillating Water Column, Time-domain, State-space, Experimental calibration and validation

1. Introduction

Wave energy is one of the most promising renewable energy resources nowadays and research is being carried out worldwide. OWC is a wave energy extraction technology based on wave to air energy conversion driven by an oscillating column of water trapped in a chamber connected to the sea. The air energy is extracted by means of self-rectifying air turbines placed on top of the chamber. Due to water level oscillations in the chamber, the air inside it is compressed and decompressed making a reversible flow towards the atmosphere and to the chamber through a self-rectifying air turbine, that rotates in the same direction regardless the direction of the air flow, and generating mechanical energy. Compared to other Wave Energy Converters (WEC) the main advantage of OWC devices is that they do not have any moving parts in the water, leading to easier maintenance works.

Since the first OWC column was built in 1910 by Bochaux-Praceique attached to a cliff next to Bordeaux (France), a wide typology of devices have been developed. Different designs have reached prototype stage. For instance, the single chamber Pico plant in Azores (Portugal) and the multi-chamber Mutriku plant (Spain) are two fixed plants nowadays tested. There

are also floating devices that have been tested in field such as the 1:4 scale OEbuoy prototype in Galway bay (Scotland) or Kaimei (1978-1986, Japan). However, OWC technology has not reached yet a fully commercial stage. Many of this full scale prototypes are testing sites for OWC turbines under development, as is the case of Limpet in Islay (Scotland), which is a clue issue for the optimization of the OWC technology. Weber (2007) addressed the problem of simultaneous scaling of hydrodynamics and compressibility effects in small scale experiments and stated that air compressibility cannot be accurately represented by geometrical scaling of the device (Lopes et al., 2009). Despite of it, some experimental analysis have been developed in OWC. Whittaker and McPeake (1986) presented the first experimental testing on an axisymmetric floating OWC based on a navigation buoy geometry and Sarmiento (1992) experimentally tested a 2D bottom-standing OWC. Later experimental studies analyzed the front well shape influence on the flow (Morris-Thomas et al., 2007) and the air flow in the chamber (Ram et al., 2010). Experimental testing of a fixed cylindrical OWC has been used for hydrodynamic model validation (Sykes et al., 2011) and a floating cylindrical OWC was tested by Sheng et al. (2012) and Sykes et al. (2011) (Gomes et al., 2012). Overall, there is not enough experimental and field data and the existing data is in general inaccessible (Alves et al., 2011). Since there is no experimental data available of fixed detached OWC devices, experimental testing was carried out in this work in order to calibrate and validate the simplified numerical model developed.

A successful design and optimization of WECs must be strongly based on numerical modeling, due to the high economic and time costs which physical

modeling entails. CFD models that approximate Navier-Stokes equations are widely accepted as being the best way of solving the dynamics involved in WEC analysis. However, their complexity leads to high computational costs. There is therefore a need to develop sufficiently accurate but computationally less demanding models. In general, the hydrodynamic interaction between WECs and ocean waves is a complex high order non-linear process, which, under some particular conditions, might be simplified. In the case of waves and device oscillations described by low amplitude motions this hydrodynamic problem is well characterized by a linear approach. Therefore, in the framework of an entirely hydrodynamic linear approach and under linear forces imposed by both the PTO and the anchoring system, the first step to model the WEC dynamics is, traditionally, carried out in the frequency domain. However, besides the interest of the frequency domain approach, in practice WECs dynamics have some parts which are strongly non-linear. Therefore, the superposition principle is not any longer applicable. Those parts include, for instance, the non-linear forces induced by the mooring system and the PTO (the main cause of the PTO non-linearities is typically the complexity of the control strategies). Thus, to account for the non-linear parts of the problem the WEC dynamics have to be analyzed in time domain. However, as currently there are no available tools to model fixed detached OWC, the objective of this work was to fulfil this gap by developing and experimentally validating a numerical tool for that purpose.

This paper presents a time-domain numerical model to assess the performance of a fixed detached OWC, opened at the bottom and with the PTO simulated by a rectangular slot in the ceiling of the chamber. The model is

based on the floating body motion equation in the time-domain. The presence of the convolution integral in Cummins (1962) equation difficults its solution in the time domain (Kashiwagi et al., 2005). To avoid this problem, one method proposed within the literature is to approximate the convolution integral by a state-space system (Jefferys, 1980; Yu and Falnes, 1995). Kurniawan et al. (2011) presented a comparison between time-domain models using different ways to face the convolution integral for some WEC concepts. In the case of an OWC device, they concluded that for an accurate direct convolution integration an extremely small integration time step was needed, since the model dynamics are stiff due to fluid (air) compressibility. They stated that a state-space approximation is an efficient and accurate alternative to avoid the direct calculation of the convolution integral. Taghipour et al. (2008) showed that using state-space models is approximately 8 times faster than solving convolution integrals. The problem has therefore moved from solving the convolution integral to finding the elements of the state-space system which approximates that convolution integral. This state-space receives as input the velocity of the body and produces an approximation to the convolution integral as an output. Several approaches have been used in the literature, such as Duclos et al. (2001), Kristiansen et al. (2005), McCabe et al. (2005) and Yu and Falnes (1995). A description of the different methods can be found in Taghipour et al. (2008). These techniques share a starting point, as all of them require the use of information taken from a 3D Boundary Element Method (BEM) such as WAMIT/WADAM (WAMIT (2012), DNV (2008)). A novel alternative, proposed by Armesto et al. (2013), does not require BEM codes, as it directly identifies the state-space which solves

Cummins equation from other sources of information such as laboratory tests or CFD simulations. The present work uses a frequency domain identification method based on Perez and Fossen (2008), Perez and Fossen (2009), Perez and Fossen (2011) and Taghipour et al. (2008) to determine the coefficients of the state-space system which approximates the convolution integral. A frequency-domain identification method (which consists of approximating the transfer function by a complex rational function) was chosen because it uses frequency-domain data directly and avoids the additional error caused by the inverse Fourier transform required to compute the impulse response function in the time-domain identification (Alves et al., 2011). This model uses the BEM to compute the added mass and damping coefficients for a given set of frequencies, and then the transfer functions associated with these frequencies are calculated. Finally, the state-space system that approximates the convolution integral can be extended to a new state-space system which completely replaces Cummins equation (Alves et al., 2011; Alves, 2012; Yu and Falnes, 1995). The new state-space receives as input the excitation force and produces the movement of the body as output.

Most of the works already available in the literature are mainly focused on independent numerical or experimental approaches. In this paper both approximations are considered and a detached OWC is experimentally tested and numerically simulated. The main objective is to develop a reliable and efficient numerical model experimentally calibrated and validated. The model presented has also been validated with IH-2VOF (Losada et al., 2008) numerical model results. In Section 2, the physics are modeled and the equations to be solved are described. The experimental testing carried out is explained

in Section 3. Validation and calibration of the new model with experimental and numerical results is shown in Section 4. Final conclusions are presented in Section 5.

2. Numerical model implementation

In this section the physics underlying the model are described as well as the model resolution.

2.1. Physics in the model

The time domain motion of a floating body is described by Cummins (1962) equation. This equation can be adapted to a single degree of freedom to represent the heave motion of the water mass inside a fixed OWC chamber.

$$(m + A_\infty)\ddot{z}(t) = \int_0^t K(t - \tau)\dot{z}(\tau)d\tau + F_{excitation}(t) + F_{hydrost}(t) - F_{friction}(t) - F_{air}(t) \quad (1)$$

where in Eq. (1) $(\dot{})$ represents the time derivative of the function, m is the water mass inside the chamber at Still Water Level (SWL), A_∞ is the added mass of the body at infinite frequency ($A_\infty = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} A(\omega)$), $z(t)$ is the heave displacement of OWC with respect to the SWL, $F_{excitation}(t)$ is the force due to incident waves acting on the OWC bottom, $F_{hydrost}(t)$ is the restoring hydrostatic force, $F_{friction}(t)$ is the friction force that takes into account the viscous and turbulent losses at the chamber entrance, $F_{air}(t)$ represents the air forces acting on top of the OWC and the integral term represents the diffraction and radiation forces. $K(t)$ is the Impulse Response Function and

represents the memory of the fluid. Table 1 contains the nomenclature used throughout the mathematics in the paper.

In the following paragraphs, exact or approximate expressions of the different terms in Eq. (1) are presented. The hydrostatic force can be expressed as $F_{hydrost}(t) = \rho g S z(t)$, being ρ the water density, g the gravity acceleration and S the chamber interior area. The friction force at the chamber entrance will be modeled as a function of the water mass heave velocity. Babarit et al. (2012) considered viscous losses as a quadratic function of the heave velocity. In this work, the following combination of linear and non linear terms is proposed for the friction force:

$$F_{friction}(t) = k\dot{z}(t) = (k_l + k_{nl}|\dot{z}(t)|)\dot{z}(t) \quad (2)$$

where in Eq. (2) k_l is the linear friction coefficient and k_{nl} the non-linear friction coefficient, both calibrated experimentally, see Subsections 4.2 and 4.3.

In addition to these forces, the influence of the air inside the chamber on the water free surface displacement must be modeled. $F_{air}(t)$ will be the force due to air pressure inside the chamber: $F_{air}(t) = \Delta P(t)S$, with $\Delta P(t)$ the dynamic pressure ($\Delta P(t) = P(t) - P_0$) and with P_0 the atmospheric pressure. Therefore Cummins (1962) equation can be expressed as follows:

$$(m + A_\infty)\ddot{z}(t) + I_c(t) - \rho g S z(t) + k\dot{z}(t) + \Delta P(t)S = F_{excitation}(t) \quad (3)$$

where in Eq. (3) $I_c(t) = - \int_0^t K(t-\tau)\dot{z}(\tau)d\tau$ is the radiation convolution integral of the product between the Impulse Response Function, $K(t)$, and

the velocity of the body, $\dot{z}(t)$. It represents the memory effects or influence of the past motion radiation and it is hard to solve directly since it needs to compute the convolution of all the past time steps. As previously mentioned, it can be approximated by means of a state-space system (see Subsection 2.2).

In this work no PTO system is considered but, as a first simplified approximation to it, a chamber top slot allowing air circulation through it has been modeled instead of the turbine that a real OWC device would have. In order to obtain the equation that describes the air pressure variation inside the chamber, the air volume variation due to free surface oscillation and the air mass flux through the chamber top opening are related by means of thermodynamics. To describe the air dynamics inside the chamber, the following simplifications are assumed: 1) Air is an ideal gas, 2) Adiabatic compression and decompression of the air and 3) Isentropic processes. The chamber here modeled has a single top opening to the atmosphere and, as previously mentioned, it has no turbines (see Fig. 5). The air mass flux through the valve must be equal to the air mass variation in the chamber:

$$\dot{m}_{air} = -\frac{d}{dt}(\rho_{air}(t)V_{air}(t)) \quad (4)$$

where in Eq. (4) $m_{air}(t)$ is the air mass in the chamber, $\rho_{air}(t)$ is the chamber air density and $V_{air}(t)$ is the air volume inside the chamber. The air volume in the chamber can be expressed as a function of the free surface position, $z(t)$:

$$V_{air}(t) = V_0 - Sz(t) = S(L_0 - z(t)) \quad (5)$$

where in Eq. (5) V_0 is the air volume in the chamber at the still water

level, L_0 is the vertical distance between the still water level and the chamber top and $z(t)$ is the internal water surface elevation or the internal water mass position in heave.

Air is modeled as an ideal gas, since it is mainly composed of nitrogen and oxygen, which under the pressure and temperature conditions considered here behave as ideal gases. The spring-like effect of air compressibility increases with the chamber height (Sarmiento and Falcao, 1985) and in addition, air compressibility helps optimize the efficiency of energy extraction (Martins-Rivas and Mei, 2009). For these reasons, air compressibility must be modeled to carry out a full scale analysis of an OWC device and is therefore considered within the scope of this work. However, the numerical model validation was carried out in small scale (the same scale used in experimental testing) and air compressibility was proved to be negligible in this scale. Chamber filling and emptying processes are considered adiabatic, since the heat exchanged with the environment is very low (Falcao and Justino, 1999). This is usual assumption when studying gas warming and cooling due to pressure oscillations. Air is considered isentropic (Falcao and Justino, 1999), which means that the entropy, or the part of energy that can not be transferred into work, remains constant during the filling and emptying processes:

$$\rho_{air}(t)(P_0 + \Delta P(t))^{-1/\gamma} = constant \quad (6)$$

where in Eq. (6) $\rho_{air}(t)$ is the air density and γ is the adiabatic dilatation constant ($\gamma = 1.4$ for dry air in the range of temperatures studied). The air mass flux through the chamber top slot can be expressed as follows (Alves, 2012):

$$\dot{m}_{air}(t) = c_d A_v \text{sgn}(\Delta P(t)) \left[\frac{2m_{air}(t)|\Delta P(t)|}{V_{air}(t)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where in Eq. (7) c_d is the discharge coefficient and A_v is the slot opening area.

2.2. Model resolution

As stated in Section 1 One particular difficulty to carry out the time domain analysis of WECs is the computation of the radiation force, as it includes a convolution between the velocity and an impulse response function. The direct computation of this convolution integral (radiation force) is typically quite time demanding. Nevertheless, the state-space representation of the convolution integral seems to be a very convenient technique to treat this problem. This method consists of replacing the convolution integral of the radiation force by a system of first order linear differential equations (ODE) with constant coefficients. Therefore, the referred advantage is more relevant if the order of the ODE system is small, which typically happens in the context of WECs.

Overall, the model is computed by means of a convolution state-space system that is extended to consider all the terms of the Cummins (1962) equation in a general state-space system. From the resolution of the general state-space system the OWC motion in time and the air pressure in the chamber are obtained. This process is explained in more detail in this subsection. Fig. 1 shows the model resolution diagram.

The radiation convolution integral in Eq. (3) represents the radiation forces and can be approximated by means of a state-space system. A general state-space has the form:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t)\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

where $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ are called input and output respectively of the state space and $\mathbf{X}(t)$ is the state-space vector. The present methodology approximates the convolution integral $I_c(t)$ in Eq. (3) by the output, $y(t)$, of a state-space system that receives the body velocity as input (Yu and Falnes, 1995):

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_c(t) = \mathbf{A}_c\mathbf{X}_c(t) + \mathbf{B}_c\dot{z}(t) \\ I_c(t) \approx y_c(t) = \mathbf{C}_c\mathbf{X}_c(t). \end{cases}\tag{9}$$

The problem now is to calculate matrix \mathbf{A}_c and vectors \mathbf{B}_c and \mathbf{C}_c that approximate the convolution integral. The first step therefore is to choose a set of frequencies $\{\omega_n\}_{n=1}^N$, and compute their damping coefficients, $\{B(\omega_n)\}_{n=1}^N$, added mass coefficients, $\{A(\omega_n)\}_{n=1}^N$, and added mass at infinity, A_∞ with a BEM code. Ogilvie (1964) provides the relations between the transfer function in time domain $K(t)$ and the added mass, $A(\omega)$, and damping coefficients, $B(\omega)$, in frequency domain. Using Fourier transform, it is possible to write the corresponding transfer function in frequency domain as a function of the added mass and damping coefficients (Taghipour et al., 2008):

$$K_{wadam}(i\omega_n) = B(\omega_n) + i\omega[A(\omega_n) + A_\infty], \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N\tag{10}$$

where i is the imaginary unit. The least square technique is then applied to find a rational function \hat{K} that approximates K_{wadam} for the given set of frequencies $\{\omega_n\}_{n=1}^N$ following the restrictions given by Perez and Fossen

(2011). The approximation is restricted to imaginary values, so if $s = i\omega$, the rational function is defined as:

$$\hat{K}(s, \theta) = \frac{P(s, \theta)}{Q(s, \theta)} = \frac{p_{n-1}s^{n-2} + p_{n-2}s^{n-2} + \dots + p_1s}{s^n + q_{n-1}s^{n-1} + \dots + q_0}. \quad (11)$$

When the coefficients $\theta = \{p_{n-1}, p_{n-2}, \dots, p_1, q_{n-1}, q_{n-2}, \dots, q_0\}$ are found by the least square method, the matrix and vectors of the state-space which approximate the convolution integral can be written as:

$$\mathbf{A}_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -q_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & -q_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ p_1 \\ p_2 \\ \vdots \\ p_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

Consequently, all coefficients of the state-space given in Eq. (9) are known. However, the heave velocity of the body, $\dot{z}(t)$, which is the input of this state-space system, is obtained solving the general motion equation (Eq. (3)) of the body at every time step, which includes the convolution integral term and all the forces defined in Subsection 2.1. Since the general

equation of motion includes the convolution state-space approximation matrices ($I_c(t) = \mathbf{C}_c \mathbf{X}_c(t)$, Eq. (9)), many authors solved the general equation extending this matrices to consider all the terms in the Eq. (3) (Alves et al., 2011; Alves, 2012; Yu and Falnes, 1995). This method is followed in this paper since it is considered the most comfortable and efficient way to do it.

In order to extend the obtained convolution state-space system (Eq. (9)) to the general one (Eq. (17)), the model equations and variables are arranged in a suitable way.

On the one hand, the general state-vector is built by including three new variables to the convolution state-vector:

$$\mathbf{X}(t) = [\mathbf{X}_c(t) \ z(t) \ \dot{z}(t) \ P^*(t)]. \quad (15)$$

On the other, the equation that describes the air pressure variation inside the chamber and completes the general state-space system is obtained combining Eq. (4), Eq. (5), Eq. (6) and Eq. (7):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{P}^*(t) &= [s_1 + s_2] P^*(t) \\ s_1(t) &= -\frac{A_v c_d \gamma}{\rho_0 S} \text{sgn}(P^*(t) - 1) (2P_0 \rho_0 P^*(t)^{-1/\gamma} |P^*(t) - 1|)^{1/2} \\ s_2(t) &= \gamma \dot{z}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where in Eq. (16) P_0 is the atmospheric pressure, ρ_0 is the air density at atmospheric pressure and $P^*(t)$ is the relative pressure: $P^*(t) = P(t)/P_0 = (\Delta P(t) + P_0)/P_0$.

Eq. (17) shows the general state-space system. This state-space system describes the general equation of motion taking into account all the forces

within Cummins (1962) (Eq. (3)), including the convolution integral, $I_c(t)$, by means of the convolution state-space system, Eq. (9).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}(t) + \mathbf{B}F_{excitation}(t) \\ z(t) \approx y(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}(t) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where the only input of the state-space is the excitation force, $F_{excitation}(t)$, and the output is the heave displacement of the body, $z(t)$. Taking into account that $I_c(t) = C_c X_c(t)$ (Eq. (9)), matrix \mathbf{A} and vectors \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} are given by:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \lrcorner & \lrcorner & 0 & \lrcorner & 0 \\ & \mathbf{A}_c & \vdots & \mathbf{B}_c & \vdots \\ \lrcorner & \lrcorner & 0 & \lrcorner & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ [\mathbf{C}_c/a] & b/a & k/a & \Gamma(t)/a \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & s_1(t) + s_2(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ -1/a \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = [0, 0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, 0] \quad (20)$$

where $a = -(m + A_\infty)$, $b = \rho g S$ and $\Gamma(t) = SP_0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{P^*(t)} \right)$.

MatLab ode15s method is used to solve the general state-space system, which is a variable order solver based on the Numerical Differentiation Formulas (NDFs) recommended for stiff problems. Alves et al. (2011) stated that generally the Matlab ode45 method of orders 4 and 5 is suggested as the best option to be used as a first try for most problems. However, in this work Matlab ode15s method was used, since it is recommended when ode45 fails or is inefficient due to the problem stiffness. The integration parameters of the solver were the default values set in Matlab (RelTol= 10^{-3} , AbsTol= 10^{-6}).

Throughout this section the time-domain model has been described as well as the way of solving the equations and all the approximations and assumptions made. The limitations of the tool proposed are motivated by this assumptions but they are also responsible for the model efficiency. The main simplifications assumed are the piston-like motion of the water mass in the chamber and the isentropic chamber filling process, since during this process air specific entropy changes from its atmospheric value due to viscous losses in the top slot (Falcao and Justino, 1999). To finish with, the linearity assumed for the excitation forces and the hydrodynamic interaction wave/device should be also noticed.

In Section 5, the experimental testing carried out for model friction and discharge coefficient calibration is described.

3. Experimental testing

3.1. *Experimental setup*

The experimental testing was carried out in the IH-Cantabria wave flume (see Fig. 2). The wave flume is 20.60 meters long, 0.75 meters high and 0.68 meters wide. The water depth in the flume was of 0.60 meters and, in order to avoid reflection, a dissipative impermeable beach was placed at the end of the flume, see Fig. 3. The experiments were carried out using the Froude's scale laws and a geometrical scale 1/30. The dissipative structure began 10 meters from the wave-maker and finished at the end of the flume.

3.2. *Measurements*

Free surface elevation was measured along the flume for reflection and transmission analysis. Their position in the flume was variable with the test period (Mansard and Funke, 1980). Due to the complexity of the free surface oscillations inside the chamber and since it was numerically modeled as a piston-like motion, spatially averaged free surface elevation time series were required. Chamber free surface elevation was characterized during the tests using special capacitive wave gauges. These special wave gauges are made of a long capacitive wire coiled over a steel framework which is able to spatially average the water free surface thanks to the capacitive properties of the wire, see Fig. 4. Each of the 3 gauges recorded a spatially averaged time series in the section in which they were placed. Due to the similarity shown in all 3 series, the bidimensionality of the experiment was proven. Two pressure gauges were used to record the air pressure oscillation inside

the chamber and an ultrasonic anemometer recorded the air velocity through chamber top slot. Instrumental setup is also shown in Fig. 3.

3.3. Tested OWC configurations and waves

A fixed and detached methacrylate chamber model was built and placed 5.40 meters from the wave-maker. It was 0.30 meters long in wave propagation direction and the chamber top opening was variable so as to simulate different resistances to the air circulation through it, see Fig. 5 and Table 2. In real scale the chamber would be approximately 10 meters long and 20 meters wide. As stated in Section 2 air compressibility is an important property in prototype scale, since it can improve power production. However, compressibility is negligible in small scale and that was experimentally proved in the experimental testing. With this aim some wave tests were carried out with chamber top slot closed, recording only very small excursions of the OWC.

A set of regular and irregular wave series with wave heights varying between 0.03 and 0.08 meters and periods between 1.1 and 3.2 seconds were tested with the different top slots, see Table 3 and Table 4. 200 seconds long simulations were experimentally run.

4. Model calibration and validation

All the numerical simulations were carried out with the same scale used in laboratory testing (1/30). Although the numerical simulations were carried out with the air compressibility terms, the influence of these terms on the calibration and validation processes (using the laboratory results) was negligible due to the model's scale.

4.1. Model verification

As a first simple verification of the time-domain model, a comparison with the frequency domain model WADAM has been carried out. The motion of the water mass inside the chamber was numerically analyzed with the top of the chamber fully opened to the atmosphere and without taking into account the viscous effects in the entrance of the chamber. A rigid body, with the geometry and density of the OWC was modeled in WADAM to obtain its motion response for regular waves with varying frequencies. Different frequency regular wave cases were also simulated with the time-domain model, feeding it with the excitation force obtained from WADAM. The mean amplitude of the motion time-series was calculated for each case and was compared with WADAM results.

Fig. 6 shows the comparison between the heave Response Amplitude Operator (RAO) of the OWC, computed with WADAM and the developed time-domain model. As expected, the oscillation amplitude is zero for short period waves and equal to the incident wave amplitude for periods larger than 2.2 seconds. According to both models, the resonance period is around 1.1 seconds for this geometry. The same value was obtained in the experimental testing. Moreover, the theoretically calculated chamber natural period agreed with this value. However, the largest difference between WADAM and the time-domain numerical model occurs for the resonance period, with WADAM predicting a 13% larger amplitude than the time-domain model. The difference around the resonance period is due to the order of the polynomial obtained to approximate the transfer function using the Matlab toolbox developed by Perez and Fossen (2009). The accuracy of the approximation

seems to be very sensitive to the order of the polynomial selected. The selected polynomial is the best approximation achieved in the full range of periods. For the rest of the periods analyzed, the difference between the models was smaller than 1%.

4.2. Friction forces calibration

A substantial step forward has been the introduction into the model of the viscous forces at the entrance of the chamber using eq. (2). Viscous and turbulent (linear and non linear) coefficients were calibrated using the results from the regular tests carried out with the maximum top aperture (5 cm). With this aperture, the pressure variations measured inside the chamber were negligible, see Fig. 7. This fact was experimentally proven by comparing chamber pressure oscillations during tests with different top openings.

By comparing time-domain model results with experimental data, different calibration curves were defined for both linear (k_l) and non-linear (k_{nl}) friction coefficients depending on the wave steepness (H wave height, L wave length), see Fig. 8:

Linear range ($H/L < 0.010$):

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} k_l = 6273527 \left(\left[\frac{H}{L} \right]^2 - 139382 \frac{H}{L} + 780 \right) \\ k_{nl} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (21)$$

Linear/non-linear range ($0.010 < H/L < 0.025$)

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} k_l = 16 \\ k_{nl} = 35 \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

Non-linear range ($0.025 < H/L$):

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} k_l = 0 \\ k_{nl} = 542715 \left(\left[\frac{H}{L} \right]^2 - 19834 \frac{H}{L} + 189 \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (23)$$

Time-domain model improvements due to calibrated friction forces are expressed in terms of the H_{m0} errors defined in Eq. (24), where H_{m0} is the zero-moment wave height, and the superscripts *mod* and *lab* refer to numerical and laboratory results respectively. These improvements can be observed in Fig. 8.

$$E(\%) = \frac{H_{m0}^{mod} - H_{m0}^{lab}}{H_{m0}^{lab}} 100 \quad (24)$$

As can be seen in the lower part of Fig. 8, the deviation between the numerical and physical results is reduced using the calibrated friction coefficient, especially for the non linear range.

4.3. Conceptual PTO calibration

The PTO systems used for OWCs are composed of self-rectifying air turbines coupled to a spinning generator. This turbine generates a resistance to the air flow that behaves as a damping force on the OWC. This damping force depends on the turbine type and on the force exerted by the alternator. As described in 3.1, in order to check the behavior of the OWC with different damping settings several physical tests were carried out with variable widths on the ceiling slot. As stated in Subsection 3.3 air compressibility was experimentally found to be negligible in the scale this work was carried out. Based on the experimental results for regular waves and a 9 mm aperture,

the top opening discharge coefficient (c_d in Eq. (16)) was calibrated. A range of c_d values was tested for each case and the difference between numerical and experimental results was computed for each try. This error between the numerical and physical model was computed using Eq. (25) where P is the pressure oscillation height, the overline refers to mean values, and the subscripts *mod* and *lab* refer to numerical and laboratory results respectively.

$$E_P(\%) = \frac{\bar{P}_{mod} - \bar{P}_{lab}}{\bar{P}_{lab}} 100 \quad (25)$$

The c_d coefficients that minimized this error for each case was considered the calibrated value.

After trying to fit different order polynomial curves to the calibrated c_d values, a parabolic fitting was selected as the best option to express de c_d values in function of the wave steepness (H/L), see the upper part of Fig. 9. The lower panel of the Fig. 9 shows the differences between the experimental data and the time-domain model results using the calibration shown. This difference is smaller than 10 % in all the cases.

4.4. Model validation

The new time-domain model was also compared with an extensively validated CFD model, such as IH-2VOF (Losada et al., 2008). IH-2VOF solves the 2DV Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, based on the decomposition of the instantaneous velocity and pressure fields into mean and turbulent components, and the $k - \varepsilon$ equations for the turbulent kinetic energy (k) and the turbulent dissipation rate (ε). The model has been under a continuous development process and subjected to an extensive validation

procedure, carried out for low-crested structures (Garcia et al., 2004; Lara et al., 2006; Losada et al., 2005), wave breaking on permeable slopes (Lara et al., 2006) and overtopping on rubble mound breakwaters and low-mound breakwaters (Guanche et al., 2009; Lara et al., 2008; Losada et al., 2008).

Calibrated time-domain model results and IH-2VOF results were compared for a decay test, due to the complication of reproducing a decay-test experimentally. The decay test was simulated with the IH-2VOF, analyzing the time evolution of the OWC vertical motion after releasing the OWC initially located 0.12 m above the SWL. In the time-domain model, the evolution of the interior water mass heave amplitude was studied. Both time series are compared in Fig. 10. IH-2VOF and the time-domain numerical model decay tests accurately agree and show a very similar motion amplitude damping in time.

After verifying that the time-domain model is capable of simulating a decay test starting with an initial surface elevation, the model was also tested for regular wave cases. Fig. 11 shows a comparison between the time-domain numerical and physical models for regular waves and a top slot aperture of 50 mm. As can be seen in Fig. 11, the numerical model accurately predicts the OWC vertical motion.

The calibration of the discharge coefficient, c_d (see upper part of Fig. 9), was proven to be independent of the top slot aperture. Therefore, results of the experimental and time-domain models for regular waves with a 4.5 mm slot aperture were compared using the same cd values of the calibration obtained with the 9 mm slot (see Fig. 12). The differences between the numerical and physical models are always smaller than 20%. As expected,

the differences between the numerical time-domain and physical model results increase with smaller chamber apertures, since the processes that take place are more complex to model. Nevertheless, based on observed comparisons, it can be concluded that the time-domain model represents well the performance of the OWC.

The friction (Fig. 8 and Eqs. (21),(22),(23)) and discharge (Fig. 9) coefficient calibration was also proven to be valid for irregular sea-states by simply replacing the wave height (H) with the significant wave height (H_s) and the mean period (T) with the peak period (T_p). To validate the calibration of the friction coefficient for irregular waves, results obtained using the time-domain numerical model with the calibrated friction were compared with results obtained using the IH-2VOF numerical model, see Fig. 13. As can be seen in Fig. 13, the IH-2VOF and the time-domain models are in excellent agreement for irregular waves.

In the same way as with friction calibration, the discharge coefficient (c_d) calibration was validated for irregular wave trains as well. Laboratory and numerical free surface and dynamic pressure spectrums were compared with both apertures (see Fig. 14). The time-domain model shows a very good agreement with experimental results. Nevertheless, the time-domain accuracy is better for the linear and weakly non-linear cases than for the non linear cases.

5. Conclusions

Throughout this paper, a time-domain numerical model used to simulate a fixed detached OWC is presented as a first step towards the modeling of

a floating multi-chamber OWC device. The aim of the work is to build a useful tool that fits the specific needs of OWC devices analysis, reaching an agreement between model complexity and computational cost. The simplified model developed is an efficient alternative to highly computational demanding CFD models, since it is accurate and much less time consuming. For instance, in the simulations carried out it was 21600 times faster than IH-2VOF on average. Model's efficiency was achieved thanks to the assumptions done, which are also responsible for its limitations. The linear hydrodynamic assumption, the piston-like motion of the chamber interior water mass and the isentropic modelling of the chamber filling process are the main simplifications considered. The model is suitable for early stages of OWC devices development, first design optimizations, scale-model design or power production estimations and definition of control strategies. The model is based on Cummins (1962) equation, which is approximated by means of a state-space system that comes from the extension of another state-space system which approximates the radiation convolution integral. In order to define the matrices and vectors that conform the state-space system, the hydrodynamic coefficients (added mass and damping) of the body are required, which are approximated based on the information got from a previous run of a 3D Boundary Element Method (BEM) such as WADAM. However, the model offers a series of advantages in comparison with WADAM: it is computationally much more efficient and it allows the inclusion of non linear terms in the equation, which is not possible with WADAM. Furthermore, the pneumatic behaviour of the chamber was also considered in the model. The simplified model was calibrated and validated using the IH-2VOF numerical

model, WADAM, and laboratory tests carried out in the wave flume at the University of Cantabria. However, air was observed to be incompressible in the experimental testing due to the small scale used. Although air compressibility was considered in the numerical model it did not affect the numerical results since the numerical simulations were carried out with the same scale as the experimental testing. Friction losses at the chamber entrance and the discharge coefficient at the top slot have been calibrated using laboratory regular wave tests. These calibrations have been validated for irregular wave trains using both physical model and IH-2VOF tests. Overall, results show the high accuracy and computational efficiency of the simplified calibrated time-domain model and therefore it can be considered a good first step towards a future modeling of a floating multi-chamber OWC device. The next steps in the development of the model will include the model extension to a multi-chamber fixed device and to validate it experimentally and/or using data from CFD models. The modelling of the floating multi-chamber device will be accomplished by coupling the motions of the OWC chambers with the motion of the device itself. Moreover, later the entire hydrodynamic linear approach will be expanded to a partially non-linear regime by assuming as valid the linear decomposition of the complete problem in diffraction and radiation problems, but treating the buoyancy and the Froude-Krylov forces as non-linear terms, while keeping the scattering and radiation forces as linear.

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References

- Alves, M.A., 2012. Numerical simulation of the dynamics of point absorber wave energy converters using frequency and time domain approaches. PhD. Thesis .
- Alves, M.A., Sarmiento, A.J.N.A., Vicente, M., Guerinel, M., 2011. Implementation and verification of a time domain model to simulate the dynamic of OWCs, in: 9th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC 2011), Southampton, UK.
- Armesto, J.A., Guanche, R., Iturrioz, A., Vidal, C., Losada, I.J., 2013. Identification of state-space for oscillating water columns (OWC) using temporal series. *Ocean Engineering* (in review) .
- Babarit, A., Hals, J., Muliawan, M., Kurniawan, A., Moan, T., Krokstad, J., 2012. Numerical benchmarking study of a selection of wave energy converters. *Renewable Energy* 41, 44 – 63.
- Cummins, W.E., 1962. The impulse response function and ship motions. *Schiffstechnik* 9, 101 – 109.
- DNV, 2008. SESAM Users Manual, WADAM.
- Duclos, G., Clément, A., Chatry, G., 2001. Absorption of outgoing waves in a numerical wave tank using a self-adaptive boundary condition. *International Journal of Offshore and Polar Engineering* 11, 168–175.
- Falcao, A., Justino, P., 1999. OWC wave energy devices with air flow control. *Ocean Engineering* 26, 1275 – 1295.

- Garcia, N., Lara, J., Losada, I., 2004. 2-D numerical analysis of near-field flow at low-crested permeable breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering* 51, 991 – 1020.
- Gomes, R.P.F., Henriques, J.C.C., Gato, L.M.C., Falcao, A.F.O., 2012. Testing of a small-scale floating OWC model in a wave flume, in: 4th International Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE 2012), Dublin, Ireland.
- Guanche, R., Losada, I.J., Lara, J.L., 2009. Numerical modelling of coastal structures stability. *Coastal Engineering* 56, 543–558.
- Jefferys, E.R., 1980. Device characterization, in: *Power from Sea Waves*.
- Kashiwagi, M., Endo, K., Yamaguchi, H., 2005. Wave drift forces and moments on two ships arranged side by side in waves. *Ocean Engineering* 32, 529–555.
- Kristiansen, E., Hjulstad, A., Egeland, O., 2005. State-space representation of radiation forces in time-domain vessel models. *Ocean Engineering* 32(17–18), 2195–2216.
- Kurniawan, A., Hals, J., Moan, T., 2011. Assessment of time-domain models of wave energy conversion systems, in: 9th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC 2011), Southampton, UK.
- Lara, J., Garcia, N., Losada, I., 2006. Rans modelling applied to random wave interaction with submerged permeable structures. *Coastal Engineering* 53, 395 – 417.

- Lara, J., Losada, I., Guanche, R., 2008. Wave interaction with low-mound breakwaters using a rans model. *Ocean Engineering* 35, 1388 – 1400.
- Lopes, M.F.P., Hals, J., Gomes, R.P.F., Moan, T., Gato, L.M.C., Falcao, A.F.O., 2009. Experimental and numerical investigation of non-predictive phase-control strategies for a point-absorbing wave energy converter. *Ocean Engineering* 36, 386 – 402.
- Losada, I.J., Lara, J.L., Christensen, E.D., Garcia, N., 2005. Modelling of velocity and turbulence fields around and within low-crested rubble-mound breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering* 52, 887 – 913.
- Losada, I.J., Lara, J.L., Guanche, R., Gonzalez-Ondina, J.M., 2008. Numerical analysis of wave overtopping of rubble mound breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering* 55, 47 – 62.
- Mansard, E.P.D., Funke, E.R., 1980. The measurement of incident and reflected spectra using a least squares method, in: 17th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE 1980).
- Martins-Rivas, H., Mei, C.C., 2009. Wave power extraction from an oscillating water column along a straight coast. *Ocean Engineering* 36, 426 – 433.
- McCabe, A., Bradshaw, A., Widden, M., 2005. A time-domain model of a floating body using transforms, in: 6th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC 2005), University of Strathclyde, Glasgow.
- Morris-Thomas, M.T., Irvin, R.J., Thiagarajan, K.P., 2007. An investigation into the hydrodynamic efficiency of an oscillating water column. *Journal*

- of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering-Transactions of the ASME 129, 273 – 278.
- Ogilvie, T., 1964. Recent progress towards the understanding and prediction of ship motions, in: 6th Symposium on Naval Hydrodynamics.
- Perez, T., Fossen, T.I., 2008. Time-domain vs. frequency-domain identification of parametric radiation force models for marine structures at zero speed. *Modelling, Identification and Control* 29, 1–19.
- Perez, T., Fossen, T.I., 2009. A Matlab toolbox for parametric identification of radiation-force models of ships and offshore structures. *Modelling, Identification and Control* 30, 1–15.
- Perez, T., Fossen, T.I., 2011. Practical aspects of frequency-domain identification of dynamic models of marine structures from hydrodynamic data. *Ocean Engineering* 38, 426 – 435.
- Ram, K., Faizal, M., Ahmed, M.R., Lee, Y.H., 2010. Experimental studies on the flow characteristics in an oscillating water column device. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology* 24, 2043–2050.
- Sarmiento, A.J.N.A., 1992. Wave flume experiments on two-dimensional oscillating water column wave energy devices. *Experiments in Fluids* 12, 286 – 292.
- Sarmiento, A.J.N.A., Falcao, A.F.O., 1985. Wave generation by an oscillating surface-pressure and its application in wave-energy extraction. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 150, 467 – 485.

- Sheng, W., Flannery, B., Lewis, A., Alcorn, R., 2012. Experimental studies of a floating cylindrical OWC WEC., in: 31st International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.
- Sykes, R.K., Lewis, A.W., Thomas, G.P., 2011. Predicting hydrodynamic pressure un fixed and floating owc using a piston model, in: 9th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC 2011), Southampton, UK.
- Taghipour, R., Perez, T., Moan, T., 2008. Hybrid frequency-time domain models for dynamic response analysis of marine structures. *Ocean Engineering* 35, 685 – 705.
- WAMIT, 2012. WAMIT Users Manual.
- Weber, J., 2007. Representation of non-linear aero-thermodynamic effects during small scale physical modeling of OWC wave energy converters, in: 7th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC 2007), Porto, Portugal.
- Whittaker, T.J.T., McPeake, F.A., 1986. Design optimization of axisymmetric tail tube buoys, in: Evans, D.V., Falcao, A.F.O. (Eds.), *Hydrodynamics of Ocean Wave Energy Utilization*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Yu, Z., Falnes, J., 1995. State-space modelling of a vertical cylinder in heave. *Applied Ocean Research* 17, 265 – 275.

Nomenclature

$\mathbf{A}(t), \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}$	general state-space system coefficient matrices
$\mathbf{A}_c, \mathbf{B}_c, \mathbf{C}_c$	convolution state-space system coefficient matrices
A	added mass coefficient
A	added mass coefficient
A_v	top slot opening area
B	damping coefficient
c_d	discharge coefficient
g	acceleration of gravity
H	wave height
H_{m0}	zero-moment wave height
$I_c(t)$	radiation convolution integral
$K(t)$	impulse response function
\hat{K}	rational function (Perez and Fossen, 2011)
k_l	linear friction coefficient
k_{nl}	non-linear friction coefficient
L	wave length
L_0	vertical distance between the SWL and chamber top
m	chamber interior water mass
m_{air}	air mass inside the chamber
P	air pressure in the chamber
P_0	atmospheric pressure
P^*	relative pressure, P/P_0
\bar{P}	mean pressure oscillation height
p_n, q_n	\hat{K} rational function coefficients
S	waterplane area of OWC
t	time variable
V_0	air volume inside the chamber with SWL
V_{air}	air volume inside the chamber
$\mathbf{X}(t)$	general state-space vector
$\mathbf{X}_c(t)$	convolution state-space vector
$y_c(t)$	output of the convolution state-space system
z	heave displacement of the OWC
ω	angular frequency
γ	adiabatic dilatation constant
τ	time integration variable
ρ	water density
ρ_0	air density at atmospheric pressure
ρ_{air}	air density

OWC model	
Length (flume longitudinal dir.)	0.30 m
Width (flume transversal dir.)	0.68 m (whole flume width)
Draft (vertical dir.)	0.20 m
Top slot (variable)	50 mm, 9 mm, 4.5 mm (whole flume width)

Table 2: OWC chamber model dimensions.

	Top slot				
	$H(\text{m})$	$T(\text{s})$	50 mm	9 mm	4.5 mm
C22	0.08	1.1	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
C23	0.08	1.2	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
C24	0.08	1.3	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
C25	0.08	1.5	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
C26	0.08	1.7	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
C27	0.08	2.2	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
C28	0.08	3.2	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
N58	0.03	1.2	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
N59	0.03	1.3	F_r cal.	c_d cal.	Val.
N60	0.03	1.5	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
N61	0.03	1.7	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
N62	0.03	2.2	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.
N63	0.03	3.2	F_r cal.	Val.	Val.

Table 3: Regular wave cases tested in laboratory and their purpose: friction calibration (F_r cal.), discharge coefficient calibration (c_d cal.), model validation (Val.).

	Top slot			
	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	9 mm	4.5 mm
Ir1	0.03	1.1	Val.	Val.
Ir2	0.03	1.2	Val.	Val.
Ir3	0.03	1.3	Val.	Val.
Ir4	0.03	1.5	Val.	Val.
Ir5	0.03	1.7	Val.	Val.
Ir6	0.03	2.2	Val.	Val.
Ir7	0.03	3.2	Val.	Val.
Ir8	0.08	1.1	Val.	Val.
Ir9	0.08	1.2	Val.	Val.
Ir10	0.08	1.3	Val.	Val.
Ir11	0.08	1.5	Val.	Val.
Ir12	0.08	1.7	Val.	Val.
Ir13	0.08	2.2	Val.	Val.
Ir14	0.08	3.2	Val.	Val.

Table 4: Irregular wave cases tested in laboratory used for model validation (Val.).

Fig. 1: Model resolution diagram.

Fig. 2: Laboratory wave flume (a) and chamber model (b).

Fig. 3: Experimental setup.

Fig. 4: Capacitive wave gauges inside the chamber (a: top view, b: front view).

Fig. 5: OWC chamber scheme.

Fig. 6: RAO comparison between WADAM and Time-domain numerical model.

Fig. 7: Experimental air pressure oscillation amplitude for regular waves of $H=0.08$ m for different periods and top openings.

Fig. 8: Linear and non-linear friction coefficient calibration depending on the wave steepness and errors with and without considering calibrated friction.

Fig. 9: Discharge coefficient calibration with regular waves using OWC with 9 mm top slot aperture.

Fig. 10: Decay test comparison between IH-2VOF and Time-domain numerical model. Initial elevation inside the open chamber=0.12 m.

Fig. 11: Laboratory and Time-domain model free surface time series. Regular waves ($H = 0.08$ m, $T = 3.2$ s, $h = 0.6$ m), top opening=5 cm, friction coefficients of Fig. 8 and Eq. (21): $k_l = 17.9315$ and $k_{nl} = 0$.

Fig. 12: Laboratory and Time-domain model free surface and chamber dynamic pressure time series. Regular waves ($H = 0.08$ m, $T = 1.1$ s), top opening=4.5 mm, $c_d = 0.8643$ (corresponding to 9 mm top slot aperture).

Fig. 13: Heave motion inside the chamber with irregular waves ($H_s = 0.08m$, $T_p = 2.2s$) and calibrated friction ($k_l = 16$, $k_{nl} = 35$). Comparison between Time-domain model and IH-2VOF.

Fig. 14: Laboratory and Time-domain model free surface and chamber dynamic pressure spectrum. $H_s = 0.08$ m, $T_p = 3.2$ s), top opening=4.5 mm, $c_d = 0.9107$ (corresponding to 9 mm top slot aperture).